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THE METHODS AND PRINCIPLES OF SETTLEMENTS DEVELOPMENT FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT LANDED-HOUSING IN BINTAN ISLAND, INDONESIA

Abstract: This study discusses the concept of settlement development for energy-efficient housing as one of the elements of the concept of sustainable development. The application of a sustainable development system in regional planning can be carried out by applying sustainable development principles such as equitable development, energy saving, ecological or environmental preservation, economic development which focuses on improving performance, and maximizing the absorption of community participation in the development process. In this case, humans must manage society and its own products, especially settlement. Hence, applying aspects of sustainable development in the conventional practice of regional planning is an important approach to reach sustainable settlement around the world. Moreover, the study of the application of this development concept is not only in the scope of the local plan as settlement, but also in the scope of the subdivision plan as neighborhood. Therefore, this study aims to study several existing reference concepts to find the methods and principles of energy-efficient and sustainable natural settlements that are suitable for application in the zone of Bintan island, Indonesia.

Keywords: sustainable settlement, regional planning, principles and methods of settlement, neighborhood.

1. **Relevance.** The Indonesian government carries out regional development through policies to accelerate economic infrastructure development. Therefore, in developing regional economic functions both in as a Special Economic Zone (SEC) and a Free Trade Zone (FTZ) were established in Kepulauan Riau province, Bintan island in the administrative territory of Bintan regency. The concept is an integrated, large scale, mega zone which can consist of port, new town, industrial, tourism, commercial and utility areas. Moreover, the types of development in the industrial sector that will be implemented, among others; mining products, textile, garment, automotive, manufacture and light industry. On the other hand, development in the tourism sector is also being developed so that it will have an impact on employment in all sectors.

In line with the development of economic infrastructure on Bintan island, it cannot be denied that there is a need to build new settlements for housing development. However, it will cause problems identified with soil, water and air pollution, waste of resources, and destruction of natural resources. Some human settlements are also subject to limited water supply, sanitation and drainage and to dependency upon toxic and non-renewable energy fuel sources and irreversible loss of biodiversity [12].

It recognized that creating better habitats involves taking precautions, preventing pollution, taking into account the potential capacity of ecosystems and preserving opportunities for future generations. It was proposed to encourage engineers, architects, designers, contractors and their customers to design and build energy efficient structures and facilities. It was noted that the quality of life depends on both the physical conditions and the spatial characteristics of settlements. The concept of "proper housing" was proposed: housing at acceptable prices, in which the created conditions for providing [14]. Consequently, it is necessary to support local governments in col-

laboration with developers to develop strategies for the provision of housing and other primary services sustainable and not lead to slum settlements in the future.

Basically, to create a better habitat, settlement development must first be increased by knowing the spatial planning on the area. Base on explanation that spatial planning is a broad term that describes systematic and coordinated efforts to manage urban and regional growth in ways that promote well-defined societal objectives such as land conservation, economic development, carbon sequestration, and social justice [4]. Spatial planning occurs at multiple geographic scales: 1) macro-regions and metropolitan areas; 2) meso-sub-regions, districts, and corridors; and 3) micro-neighbourhoods, streets, blocks. At each scale, some form of comprehensive land-use and transportation planning provides a different opportunity to envision and articulate future settlement patterns, backed by zoning ordinances, subdivision regulations, and capital improvements programmes to implement the vision [Hack et al., 2009].

Therefore, Bintan regency government issues regulation No.1 of 2020 that spatial structure and spatial patterns [5]. The definition of spatial structure is the arrangement of residential centers and network systems of infrastructure and facilities that function as a support for community socio-economic activities which hierarchically have functional relationships (Bintan Regency Regional Regulation No.1 of 2020 “Concerning the Bintan Regency Spatial Planning 2020–2040”), with the following classification:

1. Local Activity Center is an urban area that it is serves to serve district scale activities or several sub-districts.

2. Regional Service Center is an urban area that it is serves to serve activities at the scale of a sub-district or several villages.

3. Environmental Service Center is a settlement center that it is serves to serve inter-village scale activities.

Then the definition of spatial pattern is a spatial designation plan which includes spatial designation for protection and cultivation functions, with classification as:

1. Designation plans for protected areas, among others; protected forests, local protected areas, marine protected areas, lakes, reservoirs, coral reef and mangroves.

2. The designation plan for the cultivation area, among others; production forests, agriculture, plantations, mining, industry, tourism, settlements, airports and ports.

In addition, housing and settlement planning is no less important because it can create slum areas. Slum is a settlement that is unsuitable for habitation due to spontaneous planning, high building density, as well as the quality of buildings, structures and infrastructure that do not meet the requirements (Law №1 of 2011 “On Housing and Settlements” and the Government of the Republic of Indonesia №14 of 2016 “On the creation of housing stock and settlements”) [7]. Furthermore, indicators of settlements in slums can be formulated on the basis of the decree of the Ministry of PUPR № 14 of 2018, are presented as:

- 1) building condition;
- 2) environmental road conditions;
- 3) drinking water supply conditions;
- 4) drainage conditions;
- 5) wastewater system organization;
- 6) disposal of solid waste;
- 7) organization of fire protection.

Finally, to achieve the methods and principles of energy-efficient and sustainable natural settlements thus a study stage were carried out using the following methodology:

- the concept of settlement regional-based;
- principles of sustainable urban planning;
- discussion of methods and principles for settlement development;
- conclusions and suggestions on the application of settlement development.

2. **The concept of region-based settlement.** Geographically, a settlement or residence is a community where people live. The complexity of housing can range from a small number of shelters grouped together to the city center and surrounding suburbs. Settlements may include hamlets, villages, towns and cities. So that these settlements have historical characteristics when they were first inhabited, or were first inhabited by certain people. Furthermore, it cannot be denied that humans have a fundamental desire to fulfill a place of residence so indirectly the concept of settlement region-based is inseparable from the way humans choose the suitability of a settlement environment by determining what factors affect community satisfaction with the demand for habitable. The suitability of the human settlement environment as an integration of the advantages of the ecological environment, the vitality of economic development, and the convenience of public services (fig.1) [13]. More specifically, that a high quality natural environment is the basis of human settlement. Furthermore, a favorable environment for economic development is an effective support for human settlements, and no less important that a comfortable public service is integral requirements for human settlement.

Fig. 1. Conceptual model of human settlement environment suitability [13]

3. **Principles of sustainable urban planning.** The concept of sustainability is a simple and dynamic process that increasingly used in planning process however there is a common sense that sustainable development is a good thing but there is no universal acceptable ways on how this concept should be translated into practice [3].

Technical aspects of urban planning involve the application of scientific, technical processes, considerations and features that are involved in planning for land use, urban design, natural resources, transportation, and infrastructure. Urban planning includes techniques such as: predicting population growth, zoning, geographic mapping and analysis, analyzing park space, surveying the water supply, identifying transportation patterns, recognizing food supply demands, allocating healthcare and social services, and analyzing the impact of land use [11]

In its development, Bintan island has several settlements that are categorized as slum and sprawl located in coastal areas or on the outskirts of the island, based on that the selection of the concept of parcel development is more suitable for areas that have slum and sprawl. Furthermore, development parcel means the entirety of contiguous land owned by a developer, whether or not previously planned, and planned or to be planned for development as residential, commercial, industrial or recreational lands under a common scheme or plan [2]. Overall, it can be concluded that parcel is smaller than regional as regional planning deals with the larger environment.

Each community is divided into parcels, or pieces, of land then the use of each parcel of land is guided by the community zoning code. The zoning code is a set of rules that defines what

each land parcel could or should be used for (such as housing, manufacturing or open space). Zoning codes try to keep different uses from being in conflict with one another so the parcel development criteria are formulated by presented The U.S.-China CEO Council for Sustainable Urbanization, with the following main categories [9]:

- 1) environmental quality and ecological restoration;
- 2) land development and integration of urbanization and industrialization;
- 3) livable and healthy cities;
- 4) environmental protection and resource recycling;
- 5) social inclusiveness and cultural promotion.

There is one universal agreement that at an environmental scale there is no clear definition of sustainable development, and that the definition and principles of environmentally sustainable change over time. In addition, the assimilation of sustainable development principles in neighborhood planning is very important because most of the problems faced at the city macro–regions turn out to be the result of weak planning at the micro–neighbourhoods. In line with that, several efforts have been recognized to integrate sustainability in the surrounding environment. In this case, UN-Habitat proposes an approach that summarizes and refines existing sustainable urban planning theories to help build a new and sustainable relationship between urban dwellers and urban space, and to increase the value of urban land [1]. This approach is based on five principles of sustainable neighbourhoods: compact, integrated, connected. So, their are presented as:

- 1) adequate space for streets and an efficient street network;
- 2) high density;
- 3) mixed land-use;
- 4) social mix;
- 5) limited land-use specialization.

4. Discussion of methods and principles for settlement development. In determining the concept of settlement region-based, it has been mentioned about the factors that affect community satisfaction with the fulfillment a place of residence, both in the suitability of the human settlement environment as an integration of the advantages of the ecological environment, the vitality of economic development, and the convenience of public services. However, these things still raise questions about how the suitability of the residential environment with these three supporting factors; integration of the advantages of the ecological environment, the vitality of economic development, and the convenience of public services. Therefore, it is described in table 1.

Table 1

Settlement in parcel development in meso-sub-region

First level	Second level	Third level
Human settlement environment suitability	Ecological environment superiority	Environmental quality and ecological restoration
		Environmental protection and resource recycling
		Livable and healthy cities
	Economic development vitality	Land development and integration of urbanization and industrialization
	Public services conveniences	Social inclusiveness and cultural promotion

From the earliest cities to present, human settlements have been spatially divided into districts and neighborhoods (Friedmann, 2010; Smith, 2010). Existing literature introduces certain criteria that form a hierarchy of neighborhoods, while the classification schemes and nomenclature slightly differ. Different sizes of neighborhoods levels of classification could be suggested depending on their physical characteristics (e.g. size, local facilities, and recognized boundaries), composi-

tion of socioeconomic features (e.g. homogeneity/heterogeneity of income, life cycle, and ethnicity), and the degree of informal network [6].

Different sizes of neighborhoods matter when choosing different planning tools. For example, economic development tools (e.g. tax incentive programs or special use packages for sports arenas, or specific industries) are unlikely to provide the best results for small scale localized issues. On the other hand, urban design issues (e.g. pocket parks, local playgrounds, and walkability) are more likely to be effective in local residential neighborhood settings. Research has a similar quality; if it is broad scale in nature, it is unlikely to detect issues of local interest. Conversely, detailed local analysis is not well suited for broad overview policies and issues. Thus, finding an appropriate level of neighborhoods and matching planning/research goals and tools to them is critical to achieve meaningful outcomes [8]. Based on the foregoing, the authors divide the micro-neighbourhoods into five levels:

1. *Level 1*: The settlement is part of the environment outside protected areas.
2. *Level 2*: The institutional neighborhood is part of the settlement which consists of more than one unit of residential neighborhood.
3. *Level 3*: The residential neighborhood is part of the institutional neighborhood of one unit of housing.
4. *Level 4*: The housing cluster is a collection of home as part of the residential neighborhood.
5. *Level 5*: A house is a building that functions as a habitable place to live.

Based on the Law №1 of 2011 About Housing and Settlement Areas, that settlement zone need three aspects based,namely:

- 1) infrastructure, it is the physical basic equipment of a residential environment that meets certain standards for the needs of a decent, healthy, safe and comfortable residence;
- 2) facilities, it is a facility in a residential environment which functions to support the implementation and development of social, cultural and economic life;
- 3) public utilities, they are supporting equipment for residential environmental services.

Based on the source of regulation of the Ministry of PUPR, the three factors above are divided into the following categories:

- 1) infrastructure;
 - road network;
 - drainage network;
 - wastewater management system;
 - drinking water supply system;
 - solid water management system;
 - fire protection system;
- 2) facilities;
 - government facility;
 - education facility;
 - health facility;
 - worship facility;
 - trade facility;
 - cultural facility;
 - green open space facility;
- 3) public utilities;
 - electric network;
 - telecommunication network;
 - gas network.

The three aspects for the establishment of a sustainable settlement zone will be referred to based on an approach based on the five principles of sustainable environment from UN-Habitats as shown in table 2.

Table 2

Settlement in parcel development in micro-neighborhood

Principles of sustainable neighborhoods	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Adequate space for streets and an efficient street network. High density. Mixed land-use. Social mix. Limited land-use specialization	The settlement	The institutional neighborhood	The residential neighborhood	The housing cluster	The house
	Infrastructure according to its level				
	Facility according to its level				
	Public utilities according to its level				

It is well known that one of the fundamental problems in environmental damage is construction waste, so one of the most effective ways to do environmental ecology in settlements is the formation of “green” infrastructure. For several decades, various aspects of this concept have been studied in disciplines such as landscape architecture, landscape ecology and planning. During the discussion and the search for the best approaches to understanding the mechanisms, the need for interdisciplinary cooperation was realized [15]. Based on that, the planning of the integration of infrastructure elements in fig. 2 is more directed at how to manage each integrated and sustainable element at each level of the micro-neighborhood (fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Illustration of infrastructure element integration. Source picture of the Ministry of PUPR [10]

Fig. 3. Illustration of micro-neighborhood.
Source picture of the Ministry of PUPR [10]

5. Conclusions and suggestions on the application of settlement development. The basic method of region-based settlement can be adopted from the suitability of the settlement environment as an integration of the advantages of the ecological environment, the vitality of economic development, and the ease of public services. Moreover, implementation of settlement environment is carried out in an integrated manner between sectors based on spatial planning with the principles of sustainable development. Consequently, it is necessary to support local governments in collaboration with developers, in this case planners and implementers work together to develop strategies for the provision of housing and other primary services in a sustainable manner and do not lead to slum settlements in the future.

REFERENCES

1. A New Strategy of Sustainable Neighbourhood Planning: Five principles. UN-Habitats. 2014. URL: <https://unhabitat.org/a-new-strategy-of-sustainable-neighbourhood-planning-five-principles-0> (data access: 15.04.2021).
2. Development Parcel Definition. Law Insider. URL: <https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/development-parcel> (data access: 4.04.2021).
3. Dehghanmongabadi Abolfazl, Hoşkara Şebnem Önal, Shir Khanloo Nina. Introduction to Achieve Sustainable Neighborhoods. 2014. URL: https://ijac.org.uk/images/frontImages/gallery/Vol._3_No._9/2.-16-26.pdf (data access: 04.04.2021).
4. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Human Settlements, Infrastructure and Spatial Planning. 2018. URL: https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/ipcc_wg3_ar5_chapter12.pdf
5. Legal documentation and information network of Bintan regency. URL: <https://jdih.bin.tankab.go.id/index.php/Jdih/cari> (data access: 01.04.2021).
6. Park Yunmi, Rogers George Oliver. Neighborhood Planning Theory, Guidelines and Research: Can Area, Population, and Boundary Guide Conceptual Framing, 2015. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267034907_Neighborhood_Planning_Theory_Guidelines_and_Research_Can_Area_Population_and_Boundary_Guide_Conceptual_Framing (data access: 01.04.2021).
7. Pengertian dan Karakteristik Permukiman Kumuh. URL: <https://perkim.id/kawasan-kumuh/pengertian-dan-karakteristik-permukiman-kumuh/> (data access: 04.04.2021).

8. Sharifi Ayyoob. Sustainability at the Neighborhood Level: Assessment Tools and the Pursuit of Sustainability. 2013. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260038282_Sustainability_at_the_Neighborhood_Level_Assessment_Tools_and_the_Pursuit_of_Sustainability (data access 1.04.2021)
9. Sustainable Urban Planning. URL: http://www.paulsoninstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/-Sustainable-Urban-Planning_EN_vF.pdf (data access: 01.04.2021).
10. SIMANTU (Sistem Manajemen Pengetahuan). Ministry of PUPR – Indonesia URL: <https://simantu.pu.go.id> (data access: 08.04.2021).
11. Urban Planning. URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Urban_planning (data access: 1.04.2021).
12. UN-Habitat. Sustainable human settlements development in an urbanizing world. 1996. URL: https://www.un.org/en/events/pastevents/pdfs/habitat_agenda.pdf (data access: 15.04.2021).
13. Wang Yi, Jin Cheng, Lu Mengqiu, Lu Yuqi. Assessing the suitability of regional human settlements environment from a different preferences perspective: A case study of Zhejiang Province, China, 2017. URL: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321433284_Assessing_the_suitability_of_regional_human_settlements_environment_from_a_different_preferences_perspective_A_case_study_of_Zhejiang_Province_China (data access: 10.04.2021).
14. Vavilova T.Ya. Retrospective review of UN documents on sustainable development of the living environment. Vestnik SGASU. Town Planning and Architecture. 2011:1:24–28. DOI: 10.17673/Vestnik.-2011.01.5
15. Vavilova T.Ya. Review of Modern Foreign Concepts of Environmentalization of the Living Environment. Urban Construction and Architecture. 2019:9:3(36):113–125. DOI: 10.17673/Vestnik.-2019.03.15

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МЕТОДЫ И ПРИНЦИПЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ПОСЕЛЕНИЙ ДЛЯ ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОГО МАЛОЭТАЖНОГО ЖИЛЬЯ НА ОСТРОВЕ БИНТАН, ИНДОНЕЗИЯ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается концепция развития поселений с энергоэффективным жильем, которая является одним из элементов концепции устойчивого развития. Применение системы устойчивого развития в региональном планировании может быть осуществлено путем внедрения таких принципов устойчивого развития, как справедливое развитие, энергосбережение, сохранение экологии, экономическое развитие, которые фокусируются на повышении эффективности и максимальном включении общества в процесс развития. Применение аспектов устойчивого развития в традиционной практике регионального планирования является важным подходом к достижению устойчивого урегулирования во всем мире. Более того, изучение применения этой концепции развития происходит в рамках не только поселения, но и микрорайона. Поэтому данное исследование направлено на изучение нескольких существующих эталонных концепций с целью поиска методов и принципов создания энергоэффективных, экологических и устойчивых поселений, пригодных для применения в зоне о. Бинтан, Индонезия.

Ключевые слова: устойчивое расселение, региональное планирование, принципы и методы расселения, соседство.